

Impact of Mediation of Patient Safety Implementation on Safety Culture and Communication and its Influence on Nurse Performance in Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital

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ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
16 September 2023

ABSTRACT

Patient safety is a top priority that must be implemented by hospitals, however, incidents safety patients at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital still happens, this research was conducted to convey importance a safety culture and communication so that it can improve the application of patient safety so that it has an impact on nurse performance. This research purposes to uncover the mediating impact of implementing patient safety on safety culture and communication and its effect on nurse performance. This research is a quantitative research conducted with surveys, using a sample data of 100 nurses working in the inpatient room of the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital. Analysis using PLS-based SEM with approach quantitative as well as scale measuring from study before. The results of the study found that safety culture and communication positive and significant effect on patient safety and nurse performance. Patient safety proven influential positive and significant to nurse performance, as well as the implementation of capable patient safety mediate on influence not direct safety culture and communication against employee performance and nurse performance tend defined by safety culture. Advice to management Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital to avoid the attitude of accusing incidents made or reported by staff so that these incidents can make learning not happen again.

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KEYWORDS: Patient Safety, Safety Culture, Communication, Nurse Performance

INTRODUCTION

Ensuring patient safety is a top priority for hospitals, as it is closely related to the hospital's image and the safety of patients. The aim of implementing patient safety in hospitals is to safeguard patients from unforeseen events (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2017). Efforts to implement patient safety in hospitals are greatly influenced by the role of human resource providers. The human resources that have the largest population, almost 40% compared to other staff, and have the longest direct contact duration with patients are the nursing staff (Hasanbasri, 2017). As the spearhead of health services in the field, nurses play a decisive role in meeting the needs of patient safety. Professional health services available 24/7 during a patient's hospital treatment period are considered nursing services. Nurses, who regularly interact with patients, are considered vital to ensuring the success of patient safety measures. The importance of nurse performance in enforcing patient safety measures cannot be overstated in enhancing the quality of home care services during illnesses. Among human resources

components, the role of nurses is crucial for ensuring patient safety during home care for illnesses. Performance refers to the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee when carrying out job responsibilities, despite any uncertainties or lack of information provided (Mangkunegara, 2016)

Many factors are relevant to nurses performance in preventing patient safety incidents, according to the World Health Organization (2018) put forward factors organization/management that is culture safety, leadership and communication can lead to or reduce the occurrence of patient safety incidents. Culture safety is key to support performance improvement and health work in the organization. Efforts to create or build culture safety is step first in achieving patient safety. Create culture safety patient is something step beginning For minimize happening incident (Hospital Patient Safety Committee, 2018).

Failure in do communication at the time of implementation weight accept can raise serious impact that is continuous error in service nursing, treatment that is not right,

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lost information, error about plan nursing, error in supporting tests, and potential loss for patient, as well exists dissatisfaction patient to service nursing (Kesrianti, 2018). Application of patient safety as an internal mediator study This because by implementing good patient safety, it can reduce patient safety incidents by implementing effective communication in the provision of nursing care. The lack of application of nurse communication in providing nursing care is one of the causes of patient safety incidents. The behavior of nurses who lack communication, attention, carelessness, inattention and carelessness in maintaining patient safety causes errors that result in patient injury in the form of Near Miss or Adverse Events (Unexpected Events/ KTD. Lombok, 2018).

Incidents related to patient safety have occurred at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital, showing that the set standards have not yet been fulfilled. This also indicates a potential for further incidents, which could result in harm to patients. This could be attributed to the lack of implementation of patient safety target indicators in accordance with established standards. Based on this observation, the writer is interested in investigating the mediating impact of implementing patient safety practices on safety culture and communication, as well as its influence on nurse performance to prevent patient safety incidents at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Patient Safety Culture

Patient safety culture is a product of values, attitudes, perceptions, competencies, and behavioral patterns of individuals and groups within an organization (health care) that determine commitment, style and proficiency in patient safety management. Organizations (health services) that have a patient safety culture that tends to be positive can be seen from communication of mutual trust between components, with the same perception of the importance of safety, and with confidence in the magnitude of the benefits of preventive action (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2016).

A good safety culture is where nurses are actively and constantly aware of the potential for errors to occur and can identify and recognize events that have occurred, learn from mistakes and take action to correct these mistakes (Nurmalia, 2018). The characteristics of a proactive safety culture include commitment from leaders to discuss and learn from mistakes, encourage and practice teamwork, create a reporting system and provide rewards to nurses (Wardhani, 2018). According to Nurmalia (2018) indicators of patient safety culture include: culture of openness, culture of justice, reporting culture, and learning culture.

Communication

Communication is the most important part in a company, good communication within the company is very

important as the key to the success of the company itself, because every activity in the company must be communicated clearly and can be understood and understood between one party and another related party, both verbally and verbally. According to Ganyang (2018) communication is an activity of sending and receiving messages or information from one person to another in the hope that the person receiving the message or information will interpret it as intended by the sender of the message or information. Communication indicators according to Mangkunegara (2016) are as follows: the ease of obtaining information, the intensity of communication, the effectiveness of communication and the level of understanding of messages and changes in attitudes.

Patient Safety

Hospital patient safety is a system where hospitals make patient care safer. The system includes risk assessment, identification and management of matters related to patient risk, reporting and analysis of incidents, the ability to learn from incidents and their follow-up and implementation of solutions to minimize risks. The system is expected to prevent injuries caused by errors due to carrying out an action or not taking an action that should be taken (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2017). Patient safety is a condition where the patient is free from unnecessary injury or potential injury that may occur in connection with the provision of health services (Committee for Patient-Hospital Safety, 2018). Patient safety, which is a reduction in unsafe actions for patients and the provision of the best measures to obtain optimal patient health status in the health care system. Patient safety as a system (input, process and output) provides safe health services to patients and patients are totally free from physical, psychological and social injuries (Winantara, 2017). According to the Hospital-Patient Safety Committee (2018) patient safety indicators include: accuracy identification patient, improvement effective communication, improvement security necessary medication be aware (high-alert), the certainty of the right location, the right procedure, the right patient surgery, reduction risk infection related service health and reduction risk patient fall

Performance

Performance is the result of carrying out a job, both in nature physical/ material and non-physical/ non-material (Nawawi, 2015). Meanwhile, according to Wirawan (2016) performance is output generated by the functions or indicators of a job or a profession at any given time. According to Mangkunegara (2016) performance is the result of work in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with responsibility assigned to him. Performance can be interpreted as achievement or operational effectiveness an organization and employees based on goals, standards and pre-defined criteria. Performance refers to levels achievement

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of the tasks that make up an employee's job. Performance reflects how well employees meet requirements a job. Performance is often misinterpreted as effort which reflects the energy expended (Simamora, 2017). According to Ministry of Health (2017) which became reject measuring performance of nurses in incident prevention safety patient as following: prevent incident potential injury (KPC), prevent

incidents barely injuries (KNC) and prevent incidents not expected (KTD)

Hypothesis Models

The hypothetical model of the mediating impact of implementing patient safety on safety culture and communication and its effect on nurse performance in preventing patient safety incidents at the Psychiatric Hospitals Bali Province, as following:

Figure 1. Research Hypothesis Model

Based on the research hypothesis model above, the hypothesis in this study is as follows: (H1) Safety culture matters positive impact on the implementation of patient safety; (H2) Communication influential positive impact on the implementation of patient safety; (H3) Safety culture matters positive effect on nurse performance; (H4) Communication influential positive effect on nurse performance; (H5) Application of patient safety influential positive effect on nurse performance; (H6) The application of patient safety is able to mediate the influence of safety culture on nurse's performance in preventing patient safety incidents; (H7) The application of patient safety is able to mediate the influence of communication on nurse performance

METHOD

Data collection was carried out using a questionnaire. The population size in this study was 100 people an executive nurse who works in the Inpatient Room of the Psychiatric Hospitals Bali Province. The sampling technique used is the Non-Probability technique, namely purposive sampling something method For choose sample that has objective in a manner subjective.

The research questionnaire was prepared based on the results of studies and theoretical and empirical formations during the pre-research, first assessing the face and content validity, sentence and structure of each question through discussions with several staff at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital. In the process, several improvements were also made to the content of the questions in the research instrument. Furthermore, the try out involved 30 respondents to ensure the level of validity and reliability of the research instrument before it was distributed to all intended respondents. If the research instrument has been declared valid and reliable at this trial stage, then the research instrument is said to have good calibration for each variable measure studied. Then the research instruments were distributed directly to all target samples. Data obtained from the distribution of research instruments as a whole. Then examined, tabulated, filtered, and analyzed to answer and discuss research problems.

RESULTS

Based on the results of tests carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 application, an image of the research model can be presented as follows:

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Figure 2
Full Structural Model (PLS Bootstrapping)

The results of testing the research hypothesis based on the picture above are as follows:

Hypothesis Testing 1: Culture k safety (X_1) proved to have a positive and significant effect on application safety patient (Y_1). This result is indicated by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.624 with a T-statistic = 8.476 (T-statistic > 1.96) and p value = 0.000 (p value < 0.05). Based on this, hypothesis 1 is declared accepted.

Hypothesis Testing 2: Communication (X_2) proved to have a positive and significant effect on application safety patient (Y_1). This result is indicated by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.209 with T-statistic = 3,000 (T-statistic > 1.96) and p value = 0.003 (p value < 0.05). Based on this, hypothesis 2 is declared accepted.

Hypothesis Testing 3: Culture k safety (X_1) proved to have a positive and significant effect on nurse performance (Y_2). This result is indicated by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.883 with T-statistic = 26.500 (T-statistic > 1.96) and p value = 0.000 (p value < 0.05). Based on this, hypothesis 3 is declared accepted.

Hypothesis Testing 4: Communication (X_2) proved to have a positive and significant effect to nurse performance (Y_2). This result is indicated by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.065 with T-statistic = 2.048 (T-statistic > 1.96) with p value = 0.041 (p value < 0.05). Based on this, hypothesis 4 is declared accepted.

Hypothesis 5 testing: The application of patient safety (Y_1) has a positive and significant effect to nurse

performance (Y_2). This result is indicated by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.058 with T-statistic = 2.042 (T-statistic > 1.96) with p-value = 0.042. Based on hypothesis 5 it is declared accepted.

The application of patient safety (Y_1) is able to mediate the indirect influence of safety culture (X_1) on nurse performance (Y_2). These results are shown from the mediation test that was carried out, it appears that the effects C, D and A have significant values as well the indirect effect path coefficient obtained is above 0.10, which is 0.101 (Hair et al., 2014). The results of this study determine that safety culture (X_1) can affect the performance of nurses through the application of patient safety can be proven empirically. Based on these results it can be interpreted, the better the safety culture at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital then the application of patient safety will also be better so that it will have an impact on increasing the performance of nurses in Mental Hospitals Bali Province. Other information that can be conveyed is that the mediating effect of implementing patient safety variables on the indirect effect of safety culture on nurse performance partial. These findings provide an indication that the patient safety implementation variable (Y_1) is not the determining variable on the influence of safety culture (X_1) on nurse performance (Y_2) (Partially Mediated).

The application of patient safety (Y_1) is able to mediate the indirect effect of communication (X_2) on nurse performance (Y_2). These results are shown from the mediation test that was carried out, it appears that the effects

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C, D and A have significant values as well the indirect effect path coefficient obtained is above 0.10, which is 0.212 (Hair et al., 2014). The results of this study determine that communication (X_2) can affect the performance of nurses through the application of patient safety can be proven empirically. Based on these results it can be interpreted, the better the nurse's communication at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital then the application of patient safety will also be better so that it will have an impact on increasing the performance of nurses in Mental Hospitals Bali Province. Other information that can be conveyed is the mediating effect of implementing patient safety variables (Y_1) on the indirect effect of communication on nurse performance partial. These findings provide an indication that the patient safety implementation variable (Y_1) is not a determining variable on the effect of communication (X_2) on nurse performance (Y_2) (Partially Mediated).

Safety culture path (X_1) on nurse performance (Y_2) has the greatest total effect, namely 0.984 compared to the communication channel (X_2) on nurse performance (Y_2) which only gets a total effect of 0.277. These results provide an indication that the performance of nurses tends to be determined by the culture of safety that is implemented at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital. This shows that building and changing Patient safety culture is a way to build programs overall patient safety. When the focus of improvement is aimed at patient safety culture, then the outcome will be better than if focus on programs only.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the analysis, this section will discuss the results of the calculations that have been carried out. This study aims to determine the impact of mediating the implementation of patient safety on safety culture and communication and its effect on the performance of nurses in the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital. Testing is shown through existing hypotheses so as to find out how each variable influences other variables.

Influence Safety Culture on the Implementation of Patient Safety

Based on results analysis about influence cultural safety on application safety patient, show that culture k safety proved to have a positive and significant effect on application safety patient. The results of this analysis show that hypothesis 1 (H_1) is accepted. Findings This give meaning the better the culture k safety at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital will increase implementation safety patient.

Based on theory cultural influences _ k safety on application safety patient according Sorra and Nieva (2018) culture safety patient related tight with incident incident safety patient. When culture safety patient increase, incidence safety patient incident can minimized, because implementation culture safety patient can support creation of

a conducive system for maintenance health safe patient as well as free from error care nursing. This finding is in accordance with the opinion of Hasanbasri (2017) which states that building and changing a patient safety culture is a way to build an overall patient safety program. Hasanbasri (2017) also stated that fostering a safety culture has a strong potential to prevent service errors from occurring

Based on theory Kohn (2000) in Nivalinda (2019), culture safety patient developed from draft culture safety in industry. Although own different characteristics, variety study culture safety in industry become base development draft safety patient at hospital. one difference the concept is culture safety patient at hospital more focus For protect patient more big than protection to personnel that alone.

The results of this study are in line with the results of Siregar's (2019) study which found that patient safety culture is influential positive and significant on the achievement of patient safety goals in the Inpatient Installation of Hospital X. Others research, by Wigati (2020) results study this also shows influential safety culture in a manner direct and significant to performance Nurses prevent patient safety incidents at Nirmala Suri Hospital Sukoharjo

Influence Communication to Application of Patient Safety

Based on results analysis about influence communication to implementation of patient safety, demonstrated that communication proved to have a positive and significant effect on the application of patient safety, results testing This show that hypothesis 2 (H_2) is accepted. this result give meaning the better the communication which is conducted by nurse at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital will increase implementation safety patient

Based on theory influence communication nurse to quality service according to Mulyana (2019) giving service nursing to patient to patient should more take precedence interpersonal communication because this communication more focus in the process of upgrading development health patient understanding problem health patient and helpful in reach optimal health. Communication influences implementation of patient safety, according to Mustikawati (2017) communication is a determinant of the success of the nursing process so as to reduce errors that can result in patient safety incidents when implemented. Communication is very important in the nursing process if the nurse uses good and effective communication by checking the patient's identity before taking nursing action will make the patient trust the nurse besides that it can avoid unwanted incidents. Likewise, according to Pribadi (2018) communication in the world of health is sending messages between the sender and recipient with the interaction between the two that aims to foster trust, lead to safety engender satisfaction, improve treatment headed healing, because in communication give and take between patients and health workers. Poor communication

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will increase the risk of a problem, but communication skills can improve patient safety

this result support study from Yunita (2020) who found communication had a positive and significant effect on patient safety. Other research conducted by Kartika (2020) also found that communication has a positive and significant effect on patient safety in hospital

In the opinion of researchers, communication is determinant of the success of the nursing process thereby reducing possible errors resulting in a patient safety incident. Nurses who do not carry out their duties in maintaining patient safety from patient safety incidents, means that the nurse is not trustworthy in carrying out their duties. Communication is the first cause of patient safety problems. Communication in nursing services should be done effectively. This is because effective communication that is timely, accurate, complete, clear and easily understood by the recipient will reduce errors and improve patient safety

Influence Safety Culture to Nurse Performance

Based on results analysis about influence safety culture on nurse performance, shows that safety culture proved to have a positive and significant effect on nurse performance, results testing This show that hypothesis 3 (H_3) is accepted. This Findings gives meaning the better the better the culture k safety in the Bali Provincial Psychiatric Hospital will increase nurse performance. Patient safety is one of the values to ensure continuity complete health services in the hospital. Patient safety as a service does not hurt the patient nor the patient care system in a safer hospital. risk measurement, identification and management of patient health, recording and measurement cases, case learning and implementation of actions and solutions to reduce risk.

Based on theory safety culture on the performance of nurses according to Hospital Patient Safety Committee (2018) safety culture is an important part of the whole culture organizations required in health institutions. Organization with culture Positive safety is characterized by communication that is established from one another believe by shared perceptions of the importance of safety, and by beliefs about the success of preventive measures. The research results obtained are also supported by theory Hasanbasri (2017) Patient Safety culture in hospitals minimizes the possibility of accidents due to mistakes or negligence by employees. Besides that, it will increase awareness of the dangers of making mistakes or negligence. Employees working in hospitals are encouraged to go through every safe procedure and all stages of work. In addition, workers who work in hospitals are encouraged to report the slightest mistakes or deficiencies that occur to prevent accidents

Efforts to improve the quality of services in hospitals will be very meaningful and effective whenever Patient safety becomes the daily work culture of every element in the

hospital including leaders, service executors and support staff. The Institute of Medicine (IOM) states that the biggest challenge in the change movement is towards a safer health care system is changing the culture of patient safety, where a mistake is seen as an opportunity to improve care and prevent patient safety incidents. The patient safety culture in the hospital minimizes contingencies accidents due to mistakes or negligence committed by employees, besides it will raise awareness of the dangers of making a mistake or negligence. employees working in hospitals are encouraged to undergo each safe procedures and all stages of work. In accordance with results study Rahayu (2017) showing influential safety culture negative and significant to incident safety patients at Banten Regional General Hospital. The research results of Najjar et al. (2018) Finding patient safety culture to have a significant effect on adverse events, it was found that a positive patient safety culture can reduce incident losses

Influence Communication to Nurse Performance

Based on results analysis about communication against nurse performance, shows that communication proved to have a positive and significant effect to nurse performance, outcome testing This show that hypothesis 4 (H_4) is accepted. this result give meaning the better the communication nurses at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital will increase nurse performance. The results of this analysis prove that communication very important to improve the performance of nurses because communication is key for reach safety patient at hospital. Error gap communication, and influence factor humans also cause happening error in gift service health to patient. Communication in service nursing good done in a manner effective. Communication proper effectiveness, time accurate, complete, clear and easy understood by the recipient will reduce error and improve safety patient.

Communication is the most important thing and must occur between superiors and subordinates as well as fellow employees in a company. Without good communication, employees will find it difficult to carry out their jobs because it allows miscommunication to occur between employees and employees and superiors. This is reinforced by the theory according to Ali (2017) that the smoother and faster the communication is, the faster a good working relationship will be established which will improve employee performance. The opinion of the Joint Commission International (JCI) states that communication is one of the root causes of errors in medical treatment in sentinel events (Arizal et al., 2017). Effective, time precise communication, accurate, complete, clear and easy understood by the recipient can reduce error moment maintenance and upgrade safety patients (Maulita, 2019).

Failure in do communication at the time implementation weigh accept can raises serious impact that is continuous error in service nursing, treatment that is not

right, lost information, error about plan nursing, errors in supporting tests, and potential loss for patient, as well exists dissatisfaction patient to service nursing (Kesrianti, 2018) A number of study has prove that influential communication to performance nurse's performance in preventing patient safety incidents. One of them research by Maulita (2019) showing communication influential nurse negative and significant to incident safety patients at the AW Sjahranie Hospital in Samarinda. Others research, by Yunita (2020) results study this also shows communication between nurses with influence negative and significant to patient safety incidents at the City Hospital of Madiun.

Influence Patient Safety to Nurse Performance

Based on results analysis about implementation of patient safety to nurse performance, shows that implementation of patient safety proved to have a positive and significant effect to nurse performance, outcome testing This show that hypothesis 5 (H_5) is accepted. This result give meaning that the better the implementation of patient safety by nurses at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital will improve nurse performance. Application safety patient held or done with Good so service priority optimal safety and quality will give that impact broad. Especially for public will get more service quality, safe and fulfill hope them. Share hospital become mark plus for achievement standard service national and international. Safe and secure service quality too expected can increase trust public to hospital. For power health can grow values new especially important – application safety patient in every activity service provided.

The application of patient safety in hospitals is something that absolutely must be applied in line with the work culture within the organization in order to be able to reduce patient safety incidents. Prevention of patient safety incidents is an important goal of implementing a patient safety program. Reducing the number of patient safety incidents will improve the quality of service in hospitals (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2017). Behavior nurse who doesn't guard safety patient contribute to incident safety patient. Nurse who doesn't own awareness to fast situation worsened fail recognize what happened and ignore information clinical important for the patient can threaten safety patients (Lombogia, 2018). A number of studies has proved that patient safety has a significant effect on the performance of nurses preventing patient safety incidents. One of them, research by Lestari (2018) which found that the application of patient safety had a significant effect on reducing patient safety incidents. Another research conducted by Nasution (2021) found that implementation standard safety patient significant effect on the prevention of patient safety incidents.

The Impact of Implementing Patient Safety in Mediating the Influence of Safety Culture on Nurse Performance

Based on results analysis shows that the application of patient safety able to mediate the indirect influence of safety culture on nurse performance. The results of this study determine that safety culture can affect the performance of nurses through the implementation of patient safety can be proven empirically. Based on these results it can be interpreted, the better the safety culture at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital then the application of patient safety will also be better so that it will have an impact on increasing the performance of nurses in Mental Hospitals Bali Province. Other information that can be conveyed is that the mediating effect of implementing patient safety variables on the indirect effect of safety culture on nurse performance is partial where the variable is the application of patient safety not as a determining variable on the influence of safety culture.

The results of the analysis also found that safety culture has the greatest total effect on nurse performance. These results provide an indication that the performance of nurses in preventing patient safety incidents tends to be determined by the safety culture implemented in the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital. This shows that building and changing Patient safety culture is a way to build programs overall patient safety. When the focus of improvement is aimed at patient safety culture, then the outcome will be better than if focus on programs only. Other findings obtained, safety culture will be able to further improve the patient safety the better so that it will have an impact on increasing the performance of nurses preventing patient safety incidents, in application culture safety patient at hospital staff at hospital must build awareness will mark safety patient, lead and support staff in application safety patient, improve quality and quantity of human resources at hospital, apply culture that is not blame, and more look for root problem so you can done correct For avoid happening same error as well as implementation of monitoring on an ongoing basis sustainable is important thing for avoid loss information maintenance patient is part important in create culture safety patient.

A patient safety culture can increase awareness of the dangers of making mistakes or negligence, in an effort to implement a safety culture nurses are encouraged to undergo every safe procedure and all stages of work. In addition, nurses are also encouraged to report the slightest mistakes or deficiencies that occur to avoid accidents, this is done to support behavior that supports patient safety and forms an environment that supports reporting, not blaming each other, involving top level leadership and focusing on the system. Culture in health organizations is important and determines the ability to detect and handle errors that have occurred. Study earlier carried out by Anugrahini (2019) who stated

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that application patient safety capable mediate variable patient safety culture to nurse performance.

The Impact of Implementing Patient Safety in Mediating the Effect of Communication on Nurse Performance

Based on results analysis show implementation of patient safety able to mediate the indirect influence of communication on nurse performance. The results of this study determine that communication can affect the performance of nurses through the implementation of patient safety can be proven empirically. Based on these results it can be interpreted, the better the nurse's communication at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital then the application of patient safety will also be better so that it will have an impact on increasing the performance of nurses in Mental Hospitals Bali Province. Other information that can be conveyed is the mediating effect of implementing patient safety variables on the indirect effect of communication on nurse performance partial means the implementation of patient safety (is not a determining variable on the effect of communication on nurse performance.

Communication is a determinant of the success of the nursing process thereby reducing errors which could result in a patient safety incident if implemented. According to Effendy (2018) one that play a role in enhancement safety patient at home one of them is sick that is, creation culture communication is condition someone capable nurse handle something problem in work and have right as well as not quite enough answer in convey condition patient. In communication give bait come back or build trust and openness is matter important from culture safety patient

Poor communication will increase the risk of something problem, but communication skills can improve patient safety, in application culture safety patient at hospital staff at hospital must own openness communication Good communication in serve patient nor reporting incident as well as high cooperation and participation between officer health, improve quality and quantity of human resources at hospital, apply culture that is not blame, and more look for root problem so you can done correct for avoid happening same error as well as implementation of monitoring on an ongoing basis sustainable is important thing for avoid loss information maintenance patient. So that can apply culture safety more patients safe and can prevent incident that didn't desired (Dewi, 2021). Study earlier by Elrifda (2017) which states that application patient safety capable mediate variable communication to prevention of patient safety incidents.

CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion of research results it can be concluded that: Safety culture is proven to have a positive and significant effect on safety implementation; Communication has a positive and significant effect on the implementation of patient safety; Safety culture has a positive and significant

effect on nurse performance; Communication has a positive and significant effect on nurse performance; Patient safety has a positive and significant effect on nurse performance; Patient safety is able to mediate the indirect effect of safety culture on nurse performance; Patient safety is able to mediate the indirect effect of communication on nurse performance.

SUGGESTION

Some suggestions that can be given related to the results of this study include: Safety Culture already very good carried out at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital with be measured with a number of indicator. However, the learning culture indicator is the indicator with the lowest score, so several things are suggested including: Avoid the attitude of accusing incidents created or reported by staff at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital, carry out a Focus Group Discussion if a patient safety incident occurs so that the incident can make learning not happen again, Hospitals can periodically evaluate patient safety empowerment programs and patient safety culture. The patient safety team must also promote patient safety culture in the form of training, seminars or posters related to patient safety; Nurse communication related to patient safety at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital Already very good with be measured with a number of indicator, but the indicator of the effectiveness of communication is the indicator with the lowest score, so several things are suggested including: every employee in the hospital who is involved with patient care must understand the procedures for good communication, between health staff, the patient and family to prevent adverse events, the leadership of the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital gives directions to all of their subordinates regarding patient safety, the leadership of the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital considers the dimensions of communication openness and organizational learning-continuous improvement by proposing an in-house training program on effective communication for all employees including leaders

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